

KO'PHADNI KO'PAYTUVCHILARGA AJRATISH YUZASIDAN BA'ZI METODIK TAVSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bitta simmetrik ko'phadni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishning bir necha usullari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ko'p o'zgaruvchili ko'phad, ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish, simmetrik ko'phad.

Annotation: This article describes several methods of factoring a single symmetric polynomial.

Keywords: Multivariable polynomial, factorization, symmetric polynomial.

Ushbu maqolada ko'phadni turlicha usullarda ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishga oid bir qancha metodik tavsiyalar berib o'tilgan. Buni bitta misol orqali bayon etamiz.

Bizga quyidagi ko'phad berilgan bo'lib, uni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish talab etilgan bo'lsin:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc \quad (1)$$

1-usul: Qisqa ko'paytirish formulalaridan foydalangan holda ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishga harakat qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc &= (a + b)(a^2 - ab + b^2) + c^3 - 3abc = \\ &= (a + b)(a^2 + b^2) - ab(a + b) + c^3 - 2abc - abc = \\ &= ((a + b)(a^2 + b^2) - ab(a + b + c) + c^3 - 2abc = \\ &= (a + b)a^2 + (a + b)b^2 - ab(a + b + c) + ca^2 + cb^2 - ca^2 - cb^2 + c^3 - \\ &- 2abc = a^2(a + b + c) + b^2(a + b + c) - ab(a + b + c) - c(a^2 + b^2 + \\ &+ 2ab - c^2) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab) - c((a + b)^2 - c^2) = \\ &(a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab) - c(a + b - c)(a + b + c) = \\ &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab - ac - bc + c^2) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac). \end{aligned}$$

2-usul: $a + b + c$ uchhadni kubga ko'tarish formulasidan foydalanamiz, ya'ni

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b + c)^3 &= (a + b)^3 + 3(a + b)^2c + 3(a + b)c^2 + c^3 = \\ &= a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3 + 3a^2c + 6abc + 3b^2c + 3ac^2 + 3bc^2 + c^3 \end{aligned}$$

Bunga ko'ra:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 + 3ab(a + b + c) + 3bc(a + b + c) + 3ac(a + b + c) - 3abc = (a + b + c)^3$$

teglikni hosil qilamiz.

Bu tenglikdan $a^3 + b^3 + c^3$ ni topsak,

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 = (a + b + c)^3 - 3ab(a + b + c) - 3bc(a + b + c) - 3ac(a + b + c) + 3abc$$

Oxirgi tenglikning chap tomonini (1) tenglikka keltirsak:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc = (a + b + c)^3 - 3ab(a + b + c) - 3bc(a + b + c) - 3ac(a + b + c)$$

Tenglikning o'ng tomonidan umumiy ko'paytuvchilarni qavsdan tashqariga chiqarib:

$$(a + b + c)((a + b + c)^2 - 3ab - 3bc - 3ac) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac)$$

natijani hosil qilamiz.

3-usul: (1) ni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish uchun dastlab $a^3 + b^3$ ni sonlar yig'indisining kubiga keltiramiz:

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b)^3 - 3a^2b - 3ab^2 + c^3 - 3abc &= \\ &= (a + b)^3 + c^3 - 3ab(a + b + c). \end{aligned}$$

sonlar kublarining yig'indisining formulasidan foydalanamiz:

$$(a + b + c)((a + b)^2 - (a + b)c + c^2) - 3ab(a + b + c).$$

umumiy ko'paytuvchilarni qavsdan tashqariga chiqarsak,

$$(a + b + c)(a^2 + 2ab + b^2 + c^2 - ac - bc) - 3ab(a + b + c) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac)$$

natijani olamiz.

4-usul: (1) ko'phadni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish uchun, ildizlari a, b, c bo'lgan $P(t) = t^3 + pt^2 + qt + r$ yordamchi ko'phadni tuzib olamiz.

U holda:

$$\begin{cases} a^3 + pa^2 + qa + r = 0 \\ b^3 + pb^2 + qb + r = 0 \\ c^3 + pc^2 + qc + r = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

tengliklar o'rinli bo'ladi.

Umumlashgan Viyet teoremasiga ko'ra:

$$\begin{cases} a + b + c = -p \\ ab + bc + ac = q \\ abc = -r \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

ekani ma'lum. (2) sistemani hadma-had qo'shib yuborsak:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 + p(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) + q(a + b + c) + 3r = 0$$

p, q va r larni o'rniga mos qiymatlarni qo'yib qo'ysak:

$$\begin{aligned} a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) + \\ + (ab + bc + ac)(a + b + c) - 3abc = 0 \\ a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc = \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) - (a + b + c)(ab + ac + bc) = \\ &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac). \end{aligned}$$

natijani olamiz.

5-usul: Qiymati (1) ifodaga teng quyidagi determinantni tuzib olamiz:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} a & b & c \\ c & a & b \\ b & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (4)$$

determinant xossasiga ko'ra 2-va 3-ustunlarni 1-ustunga qo'shib, determinant xossasidan foydalansak:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} a + b + c & b & c \\ a + b + c & a & b \\ a + b + c & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$(a + b + c) \begin{vmatrix} 1 & b & c \\ 1 & a & b \\ 1 & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac).$$

kelib chiqadi.

6-usul: (1) ifoda simmetrik ko'phad bo'lganligi uchun simmetrik ko'phadlar haqidagi asosiy teoremdan foydalanamiz: (1) ko'phadning eng birinchi hadi a^3 bo'lganligi uchun

$$\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 & \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 & & \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_1^3 & & \\ 2 & 1 & 0 & \sigma_1 \sigma_2 & & \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \sigma_3 & & \end{array}$$

bu yerda l_1, l_2, l_3 lar mos nomalumni darajalari

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= a + b + c \\ \sigma_2 &= ab + bc + ac \\ \sigma_3 &= abc \end{aligned}$$

bundan (1) ni elementar simmetrik ko'phadlar orqali ifodalasak:

$$f(a, b, c) = \sigma_1^3 + A\sigma_1\sigma_2 + B\sigma_3 \quad (7)$$

a, b, c ga qiymat berib funksiya va elementar simmetrik ko'phad qiymatlarini topsak:

$$\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} a & b & c & f & \sigma_1 & \sigma_2 & \sigma_3 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 2 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

Topilgan qiymatlarni (7) ga qo'ysak:

$$0 = 27 + 9A + B \quad \text{bundan esa} \quad 2 = 8 + 2A \quad \text{bo'ladi.}$$

Bu ifodalardan $A = -3, B = 0$ ekanligini topamiz. Natijada:

$$f = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2 = \sigma_1(\sigma_1^2 - 3\sigma_2)$$

σ lar qiymatlarini olib kelib qo'ysak:

$$(a + b + c)((a + b + c)^2 - 3ab - 3bc - 3ac) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac)$$

natija kelib chiqadi.

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